

PREVALENCE OF VAGINAL CANDIDIASIS AMONGST FEMALE PATIENTS ATTENDING FEDERAL MEDICAL CENTER KEFFI, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The research work was carried out to determine the prevalence of vaginal Candidiasis amongst female patient attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi. The study includes all class of female excluding children below the age of 15. Prior to this study, written informed consent was obtained from the research and ethics committee of Federal Medical Centre, Keffi. Candida albicans is an opportunistic fungal pathogen that exists as harmless commensal in the gastrointestinal and genitourinary tracts in about 70% of human and about 75% suffer from Candida infections at least once in their life time. It becomes an opportunistic pathogen for immunocompromised patients, for some immunologically weak individuals, or even for healthy persons. Candidiasis has emerged as a significant medical problem because of advance in modern medicine owing to a discriminate long-term uses of antibiotics, immunosuppressive and cytotoxic therapies. This study assesses the Prevalence of Candida albicans among Female Patients in Federal Medical Centre, Keffi L.G.A., Nasarawa State, Nigeria. A systematic random sampling technique was used to select 100 female patients at the age of 15 years above. Only patients who showed no symptoms of urinary tract infections and who were not on antifungal therapy at the time of the study were included in the study. High Vaginal Swab (HVS) was aseptically collected from each of the patients using a sterile swab stick. The collected samples were labelled appropriately, cultured and evaluated for the presence of Candida albicans. Candida albicans was detected in 30% of the subjected 100 samples.*

Introduction

Background of the study

The genital tract is the portal of entry for numerous sexually and non sexually transmitted diseases. Different kinds of

bacterial and non bacterial infections exist that affect the female reproductive tract and causes vaginal discharge. Vaginal discharge is common in primary health care and often the second

most common gynaecological problems after menstrual disorders (Uzoh *et al* 2016).

Candida albicans is an opportunistic fungal pathogen that exists as a harmless commensal in the gastrointestinal and genitourinary tracts in about 70% of human and about 75% suffer from *Candida* infection at least once in their life time. *Candida albicans* are small, oval yeast measuring 2-4mm in diameter (Kabir *et al* 2012). The distribution of *Candida albicans* is widely in normal and healthy individuals and is usually found in the mouth, skin, gastrointestinal and urinogenital tracts of females where they exist as normal flora (Nwachukwu *et al* 2020). However, it becomes an opportunistic pathogen for immunocompromised patients, for some immunologically weak individuals, or even for healthy persons. The infection caused by *Candida albicans* is known as Candidiasis (Kabir *et al* 2012). Under normal circumstance, the *Candida* yeast is held in check by normal body defenses together with other members of the normal flora. For instance, acidity of the vaginal is maintained at pH 4.0-4.5 to prevent some vaginal pathogens from establishing and causing infection (Okonkwo and Umeanaeto 2010).

Statement of the problem

Candidiasis is an opportunistic fungal infection caused by the fungi called *Candida*, which can affect the oral cavity, vagina, penis (*Candida balanitis*) or other parts of the body. Untreated *Candida* infection carries the risk of leading to a systemic infection in which other organs can become involved and may lead to sepsis.

Justification of the study

The study will be useful in detecting the prevalence of vaginal Candidiasis in female patients, which are narrowed to the Federal Medical Centre, Keffi.

The study will be a tool for the establishment of intervention strategies that will help in reducing the risk of vaginal yeast infection among the study population which comprises basically of females.

Aim of the study

The aim of the study is to determine the prevalence of vaginal Candidiasis among female patients attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria and to create strategies to offer early diagnosis and prompt treatment to avoid adverse effects which could be destructive if not properly managed.

Objectives of the study

Specific objectives of the study include:

1. To determine the prevalence of candidiasis among female patients attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, Nasarawa State.
2. To determine the associated risk factors of candidiasis among females in the study area.

Literature review

Epidemiology

According to previous epidemiological studies, *Candida albicans* is the most common species of *Candida*. *Candida albicans* can be identified by culture obtained from sample of female patient. It involves the over growth of the yeast or fungus. The organism is found normally in the small gut, on the skin, in the large intestine and the vagina.

Candida albicans are normal floral, however they give rise to infection when there is an over growth.

Vaginal candidiasis is an infection that affects a wide range of females all over the world. It is an infection that is asymptomatic at the point of contraction. *Candida albicans*, a fungus, causes health hazards when neglected.

Candida vulvovaginitis is common. It is responsible for a third of all cases of vulvovaginitis in reproductive-aged women, and 70% of women report having had Candida vulvovaginitis at some point in their lifetimes. About 8% of women suffer recurrent Candida vulvovaginitis (Rebecca *et al* 2023). The most common responsible pathogen is *C. albicans* (in about 90% of cases), with most of the remaining cases caused by *Candida glabrata*.

Classification of *Candida albicans*

Superkingdom: Eukarya

Kingdom: Fungi

Subkingdom: Dikarya

Phylum: Ascomycota

Subphylum: Saccharomycotina

Class: Saccharomycetes

Subclass: Saccharomycetidae

Order: saccharomycetales

Family: Debaryomycetaceae

Genus: *Candida*

Species: *albicans*

Candidiasis was discovered by Langenbeck in 1839 (Felemban *et al* 2019).

Transmission and risk factors

Candidiasis can occur due to conditions that affect the immune system. For examples in takes of antibiotics change the normal balance between the organisms in the vagina by reducing the number of lactobacilli which help keeps yeast level in check.

Factors that increase the risk of developing a yeast infection include:

Antibiotic use, increased estrogens level, uncontrolled diabetes, impaired immune system, use of scented soaps and deodorants on the vagina.

Signs and symptoms

There are various signs and symptoms experienced by a person who had been infected with candidiasis. These are:

Itching and irritation in the vagina and vulva. A burning sensation especially during intercourse or urinating. Redness and swelling of the vulva. Vaginal pain and soreness. Vaginal rash. Thick, white, odour-free vaginal discharge with a cottage cheese appearance. Watery vaginal discharge. Pain during sex.

Diagnosis

To diagnose for the presence of yeast infection, the doctor or health care provider may have to ask certain questions about medical history of past vaginal infections or sexually transmitted infections.

A pelvic examination will also be done by the doctor. This is achieved by examining the external genitals for signs of infections. It may show inflammation of the skin of the vulva, within the vagina, and on the cervix or dry, white plaques on the vaginal wall.

Next, a speculum could be used to hold the vaginal walls open to examine the vagina and the lower, narrower part of the uterus called the cervix.

Candida albicans is commonly pass from mother to her infant during childbirth, and exist as part of a normal human's microflora. The overgrowth of *Candida albicans* cause symptoms of disease, like when there are imbalances for example, changes in the normal vaginal pH (Felemban *et al* 2019).

Treatment of *Candida albicans* infection

There are numerous current therapeutic options available for the treatment of Vulvovaginal candidiasis that vary based on uncomplicated or complicated presentation. Treatments mainly consist of prescription oral dosage forms, or over-the-counter topical preparations, or vaginal suppositories (Williams *et al* 2020).

Antifungal drugs

Azoles are the most common class of antifungal drugs used to treat vaginal candidiasis due to their good bioavailability, antifungal efficacy, and relative safety. However, the azoles class exhibits static activity (Willems *et al* 2020). The available drugs and drug use are;

I. **Itraconazole.** An intravenous preparation of itraconazole in hydroxy-propyl- β -cyclodextrin has been licensed. It is well known to be active against mucosal forms of candidiasis, but an intravenous form of itraconazole allows for treatment of invasive disease (Pappas *et al* 2004).

II. Voriconazole and the newer azole antifungal agents.

Voriconazole is available in both oral and parenteral preparations. It is as active as fluconazoles against esophageal candidiasis, although it was associated with more adverse events in a recent study. The in vitro anti – *Candida* activity of the other azoles under active development (posaconazole and ravuconazole) also appears to be good (Pappas *et al* 2004).

III. Caspofungin and the echinocandin antifungal agents.

Caspofungin is the first of the echinocandin antifungal agents to be licensed. This agent is

only available as a parenteral preparation, and its spectrum is largely limited to *Candida* and *Aspergillus* species. The in vitro activity of the other 2 agents in this category (anidulafungin and micafungin) against *Candida* species (Pappas *et al* 2004).

IV. Amphotericin B deoxycholate and the lipid-associated formulations of amphotericin B

Although amphotericin B deoxycholate has long been the standard agent for treatment of invasive candidiasis, the toxicity of this preparation is increasingly appreciated. Lipid-associated preparations have previously been considered primarily for patients who are intolerant of or have an infection refractory to the deoxycholate preparation (Pappas *et al* 2004).

Therapy for *Candida albicans* infection

Recently, there is a growing interest in nanoparticle material, which different from the conventional therapy (Felemban *et al* 2019). Probiotic therapy, or the administration of beneficial microbes to the mucosal surface, has been suggested for the treatment or prevention of *Candida* vaginitis (Willems *et al* 2020). The therapies are;

i. Nanotechnology:

Application depending on the usage of materials in the nanometer scale known as nanotechnology that permit engineering to control nanomaterial which have physiochemical properties and interacts with biological systems.

ii. Probiotic therapy:

Probiotic therapy, or the administration of beneficial microbes to the mucosal surface, has been suggested for the treatment or prevention

of *Candida* vaginitis. A study by Pericolini and colleagues has found that introduction of *S. cerevisiae* to the murine vagina could help protect against *Candida albicans* challenge.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was carried out in Keffi local government area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Keffi is 68km² from Abuja the Federal Capital and about 128km² from Lafia, the state capital. Keffi has geo-coordinate of 8.84N^o and 7.87E^o and it is situated at elevation of 321 meters above sea level.

Keffi has a population of 85,911 making it the 2nd biggest city in Nasarawa State (Wikipedia 2016). The sample was collected and analysed at the Medical Laboratory, Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Study Population

One hundred (100) female patients were randomly recruited for this study. The study population comprised of female patients attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, Nasarawa State.

Sample size calculation

Due to unavailability of data on the true prevalence of the infection among students in Nasarawa State University, at a prevalence of 3.69% (0.0369) based on the previous study of Emeka *et al.* (2014) was used to determine the sample size using the formula by Niang *et al.* (2006) at 0.05 level of precision.

$$n = Z^2pq/d^2$$

Where;

n= derived minimum sample size if the target size population is > 10 000.

Z= standard normal deviation at the required confidence interval (1.96) which corresponds to 95% confidence interval.

p= Prevalence rate of 0.00369 (3.69%) from Emeka *et al.* (2014)

$$q = 1 - p$$

$$q = 1 - 0.0369$$

$$q = 0.9631$$

d²= degree of accuracy/ precision expected i.e. 0.05 and

Therefore, p=0.0369

$$n = 1.96^2 (0.039) (0.9631) / 0.05^2$$

$$n = 3.84 (0.0355) / 0.0025$$

$$n = 0.1363 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 54.52$$

$$n = 54.$$

However, 100 samples were collected for this research study.

Ethical Consideration

Clearance from the ethical committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, Nasarawa State was obtained in accordance with the code of ethics for biomedical research involving human subjects.

Exclusion and Inclusion Criteria

This research excludes children below 15 years and women with suppressed immune system.

It includes other class of women.

Specimen collection

Prior to this study, written informed consent was obtained and socio-demographic and risk assessment information was collected on self-administered questionnaires.

High vaginal swab samples were collected from female patients using a swab stick and preserved in physiological saline.

Samples were each placed in the swab stick container and preserved with normal saline and stored at 37°C until analysed within 24 hours.

Preparation of Samples for Analysis

Vaginal swab samples collected from patients were cultured and yeast identification and antifungal susceptibility test was carried out to determine the presence of the yeast infection. Samples collected from the patients were analysed using microscopy, culture and susceptibility testing. Gram tube tests were also carried out to ascertain the particular specie of *Candida* (*C. albicans*).

Materials:

Media: The media that was used in this study are; Sabouraud Dextrose Agar, Serum-human venous blood, chocolate agar and CLED agar.

Reagent: The reagents which were used for this study are Crystal violet, Lugols iodine, Acetone-alcohol and Neutral red.

Glass wares and Equipment

Glass wares or equipment such as Petri-dish, conical flask, Beakers, Cover slip, Glass slide, Measuring Cylinder, test-tube rack, test-tubes, weighing balance, autoclave, wire loop, incubator, hot air oven, microscope, Bunsen burner, refrigerator, centrifuge, Microscope, swab stick, wash bottle containing sterile water.

Method

The vaginal swab samples were collected from the female patients using sterile swab sticks, having obtained an informed consent from the patients' laboratory. The samples were analysed in the Medical Laboratory in Federal Medical Centre, Keffi.

The swabs were cultured in Sabouraud dextrose agar, Blood agar, CLED and Chocolate media under sterile condition at 37°C for 24 hours after which the swabs were preserved in physiological saline.

Preparation of agar

Sabouraud dextrose agar was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions (65g) of the agar. It was suspended in 1000ml of distilled water and was mixed well until a uniform suspension was obtained. It was heated with frequent agitation and boiled and then sterilized at 118-121°C for 15 minutes (Saigal *et al* 2018).

Nutrient agar was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions (28g). 28g of nutrient agar powder was dissolved in distilled water. The mixture was heated while stirring to dissolve the components. The mixture was autoclaved after wards at 121°C for 15 minutes. It was allowed to cool not solidify (<https://microbiologyinfo.com/nutrient-agar-composition-preparation-and-uses>).

Inoculation and Identification of *Candida albicans*

The High Vaginal Swabs samples was streak directly onto Sabouraud dextrose agar plates and will be incubated aerobically at 37°C for 48hours. Yeast growth characteristics of creamy, greyish-white colonies were obtained. (Nwachukwu *et al* 2020).

Gram staining

A thin smear of the *Candida* culture on a clean grease free slide was heat-fixed, air-dried and then flooded with few drops of crystal violet and allowed for 1 minute. The slide was gently washed in an indirect stream of tap water for 2

seconds. The slide was flooded with a mordant (Gram's iodine) for 1 minute. The slide was flooded again with a gently indirect stream of tap water for 2 seconds. The slide will be flooded with a decolorizing agent (Acetone-alcohol decolourizer) for 10-15 seconds, until decolorizing agent running for the slide runs clear. The slide was counterstained with neutral red for 1 minute. The stain was washed out gently in an indirect stream of tap water until no colour appears in the effluents, and then blotted dry with absorbent. Oil immersion will be applied and the slide will be examined using x100 in a bright field microscope. Gram staining results show 4-6mm in size of *Candida albicans* with oval shapes (Nwachukwu *et al* 2020).

Germ tube test

Serum-human venous blood was collected and allowed to be fully clotted. The specimen was placed vertically in a test tube rack to speed up the clotting action. After clotting, the specimen was placed in a centrifuge machine at 3000rpm for 10minutes (Saigal *et al* 2018).

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed with the Statistical Package for Social sciences (SPSS) software version 2.0, using analysis of variance procedure and simple descriptive and inferential statistics of tables, Frequencies and percentages (Nwachukwu *et al* 2020).

Prevalence and socio demographic tables were calculated for the study population and separately by their age range, age group, educational status, occupational status and marital status. The results was computed, analysed and computed.

Table 4.1: Morphological characteristics of *Candida albicans* isolate from High vaginal swab of female patients attending Federal Medical Centre.

RESULTS

Introduction

The research was carried out according to the materials and methods presented at the previous chapter. The expected result of the research from the hundred (100) samples of the female outpatients attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi is represented in tables below and the findings were analyzed in the form of percentages tables.

Result interpretation

Table 4.2.1 shows the morphological features of *Candida albicans* isolate. Gram staining results showed about 4-6µm in size of *Candida albicans* with oval shapes and Formation of germ tube. Positive *Candida albicans* growths were characterized by smooth greyish-white colonies. The results showed that out of 100 female patients examined, 30 were infected and their samples showed the growth of *Candida albicans* after undergoing germ tube test (Table 4.2.2). The prevalence of the *Candida albicans* decreases with increasing age. The age group with the highest prevalence was ≥15-25 (35.7%) while age group 26-40 (30.4%) follows next with the least being ≥41 (23.0), (Table 4.2.3). Patients with tertiary level of education had the lowest prevalence of candidiasis with a prevalence of 22.2% as shown in table 4.2.4. Table 4.2.5 shows the occupational status of the respondents has parameters such as housewife with a prevalence of 23.3%, business women or self employed with a prevalence of 29.7%, civil servant with a prevalence of 39.1 and student with a prevalence of 39.1%.

Laboratory test	Inference
Culture on SDA	smooth, grayish-white colonies
Germ tube formation	yes
Gram staining (blastocondia or pseudohyphae)	4-6µm, oval shapes or rod shapes

SDA= Sabourand Dextrose Agar

Table 4.2: Total number of female patients examined from October-December, 2023 and January, 2024.

History of Candidiasis	Number examined (n)	Number positive	Prevalence (%)
Young women <35	68	18	26.4
Older women >35	32	12	37.5
Total	100	30	30.0

P-value = 0.2755

Table 4.2.2. The total number of female patients examined from October-December, 2023 and January, 2024 in Federal Medical Center, Keffi

who had vaginal *Candidiasis* was 30 with prevalence of 26.4% for young women and 37.5% for older women.

Table 4.3. Prevalence of *Candida albicans* amongst female patients according to age group attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi.

Age group (years)	Number of Participants	Number Infected	Prevalence (%)
15-25	28	10	35.7
26-40	46	14	30.4
≥ 41	26	6	23.0
Total:	100	30	30.0

P-value = 0.2755

Table 4.4. Educational status of female patients attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, with history of candidiasis.

Level Of Education	Number examined (n)	Number positive	Prevalence (%)
Tertiary	9	2	22.2
Secondary	21	5	23.8
Primary	33	9	27.2
No formal education	37	14	37.8
Total	100	30	30.0

P-value = 0.04656

19.200

Table 4.5: Occupational status of female patients attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, with a history of Candidiasis

Occupational status (%)	Number examined (n)	Number positive	Prevalence
House wife	30	7	23.3
Business women or self employed	37	11	29.7
Civil servant	10	3	30.0
Student	23	9	39.1
Total	100	30	30.0

P-value = 0.1188

Figure 4.7: Marital status of female patients attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, with history of Candidiasis

Marital status	Number examined (n)	Number positive	Prevalence (%)
Married	68	22	32.2
Single	32	8	25.0
Total	100	30	30.0

P-value = 0.1188

DISCUSSION, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

DISCUSSION

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS IN RELATION TO OBJECTIVES

CONSIDERED

Total number of respondents studied

The number of women who attended the medical centre for this purpose was above one hundred (100). However for the purpose of the research, 100 outpatients were randomly selected, with 30% of them presenting with Vaginal candidiasis with germ tube test presenting at the presence of *Candida albicans* and those who weren't infected were 70%. In my study, the prevalence was found to be 30%. The

prevalence of vaginal candidiasis was also reported by other studies to be 19% (Aring *et al*). In table 4.2.4, it is clear that the age group with the highest infection of *Candida albicans* is 15-25 (35.7%). Next are those within the range of 26-40 (30.4%) and with the least range ≥41 (23.0%). This might be because of their youthful sexual escapades or immune system.

Educational status

The women with no formal education had the highest rate with 37% followed by the ones with primary school education with 33%, then the ones with secondary school. The higher the level of education, the lower the prevalence of *Candida albicans* infection.

Occupational status

Out of the studied population, 30% were housewives, 37% were business women or self employed, 10% were civil servants while the remaining 23% were students. The married women are more infected (27%), than the single women (25%).

Marital status

The rate of married women who are more prevalent to the disease of study is high compared to those that were single.

Conclusions

Younger women are more vulnerable to vaginal candidiasis irrespective of their occupational status, educational status and marital status.

Recommendation Perfumed or medicated soap, shower gels and vaginal deodorants shouldn't be used to wash the vulva. This is because it leads to a change in the pH of the vagina leading to an overgrowth of *Candida spp* capable of resulting to candidiasis. Use just water. Scented tampons and pads should be avoided as well.

1. Douching should be avoided. This is because it contributes in the removal of normal bacteria which protects the vagina, thus exposing the vagina to infections.
2. Early diagnosis and adequate treatment of vaginal candidiasis should be practiced.
3. Good personal hygiene practice should be observed among women as it helps to reduce the risk of vaginal yeast infection

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